

Investigation and Application of Robotics and Automation System for Construction Machinery and Environmental Monitoring

Oscar Chijioke Nkwazema¹, Liu Yin^{1*}, Mariama Janneh²

¹School of Mechanical Engineering and Electronic Information, China University of Geosciences, 430074, Wuhan China.

²School of Environmental Science and Engineering, China University of Geosciences, 430074, Wuhan China.

Accepted July 27, 2021

Published July 30, 2021

*Corresponding Author:

Liu Yin

Liuyin40@163.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5148629>

Pages: 120-130

Funding: Self

Distributed under
Creative Commons CC BY 4.0

Copyright: © The Author(s)

How to cite this article (APA):
Nkwazema, O. C., Yin, L., & Janneh, M. (2021). Investigation and Application of Robotics and Automation System for Construction Machinery and Environmental Monitoring. *North American Academic Research*, 4(7), 120-130. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5148629>

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The objective of this article is to examine present and upcoming automation options for automating on-site construction processes via the use of digital technology. We performed empirical and theoretical investigations. A review of the literature was undertaken to acquire insight into the construction industry's digitalization and overall level of automation. This was subsequently supplemented with an interview study, in which a Technical Specialist from Skanska AB served as one of the interviewees in addition to serving as the thesis's mentor. Skanska was selected as a typical construction business since it is one of the largest in the world. To broaden the data collection, the interview research included representatives from many relevant firms, who were questioned about their own state of digitalization and automation.

According to the findings of these research, the construction sector has obstacles in implementing automation technologies. Lack of data in general, safety issues, and project planning activities are all examples of this. Existing industrial robots, for example, are often heavy and have a poor lifting capacity to weight ratio, which isn't an issue in a production context but makes for an inconvenient fit in the construction sector, where movability and great lifting capacity are desired. This thesis covers the various technologies for adopting automation at the construction site, as well as the benefits that may be expected from successful implementations, such as improved productivity, increased profitability, and increased safety for both equipment and workers.

Keywords: CONSTRUCTION AUTOMATION, ROBOTICS

Introduction

For the past four decades, the world of automation has developed at a breakneck pace, propelled by rising user expectations, technological advancements, and the maturation of industrial process technologies (Mehta & Reddy, 2015). Automation as a strategic advantage is enabled by a balance of quality, productivity, flexibility, and cost (ibid.).

Due to the irregularities of human nature, fully automated procedures produce great outcomes, whereas semi-automated and manual processes produce varying results (Sharma 2011).

(Eastman et al. 2008) Digital technology offers data for automated production methods. Automation benefits from networked control systems and information across a plant, according to (Mehta & Reddy, 2015), so that activities may be fully integrated.

In terms of digitization and automation, the construction sector lags behind other industries (Oesterreich & Teuteberg, 2016). Automation is made possible through digitalization.

According to (Richards 1994), in order for automation and robotics to become increasingly common in the construction sector, computer models including all of the essential information to generate information databases for use in subsequent construction phases are required.

Furthermore, it is well known that the construction sector is lagging behind many other industries in terms of productivity gains (Fulford & Standing, 2014). According to Garca De Soto et al. (2018), there are numerous causes for the global reduction in construction productivity, including reluctance to change, which derives from the construction industry's conventional nature. Furthermore, the construction sector suffers from inadequate teamwork, limited data sharing, and rapid turnover, making innovative technique adoption difficult. Furthermore, in the construction business, innovation moves at a glacial pace (Bock 2015; Bogue 2018; Wu et al. 2016).

According to (Wu et al. 2016), the construction sector is regarded as a low-tech business. Long product life cycles, goods with significant variability and complexity, variety of dimensions, and a permanent construction site are all possible causes for the sluggish rate of innovation (Bock, 2015). A lack of willingness to apply new tactics, as well as a limited research and development budget, contribute to the sluggish rate of innovation (Bock, 2015). (Smith and Tardif 2009) found that the global construction sector has made minimal technical progress. Although construction has been slow to develop and deploy automation in comparison to other industries, robots in building are not totally new. Robots were being used to destroy concrete, dig tunnels, grind concrete, transport cargo, and clean floors as early as the late 1980s (Rahm 1988). According to (Fulford & Standing 2014), the construction sector has a lot of room for productivity improvements, and cooperation is one factor that can help.

After seeing the advantages of automation in the manufacturing business, it's easy to imagine what automation may mean for the building industry. According to (Vähä et al. 2013), automation in construction should contribute to improved production, performance, safety, quality, and value. According to (Bouge 2018), construction automation (CA) has the potential to provide significant operational, environmental, and economic advantages. Some have recognized the potential benefits, and according to (Bonev et al. 2015), methodologies and concepts from the automobile sector have been attempted to be applied into construction research for some time in order to achieve improved productivity.

The need for automating time-consuming, dangerous, and repetitive operations has grown in a complex and labor-intensive industry like construction (Panda et al. 2017). Workers with the appropriate education or

outstanding talents have never been more valuable than they are now, since they can generate value via the use of technology (Autor 2015).

In terms of construction site safety, it is typical for construction workers to suffer from musculoskeletal system injuries, which impair mobility in the human body and are referred to as musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) (Dzeng et al. 2017).

MSDs are frequently produced by cumulative and repetitive stressful motions or by lifting heavy equipment quickly, leading in fatigue (Dzeng et al. 2017). Construction is one of the most risky industries for employees in many nations (Poh et al. 2018). Construction employees are exposed to a risky and difficult working environment, with a higher rate of injuries and deaths than workers in other industries (Barker et al., 2004; Zou et al., 2017). In the UK, 65,000 construction workers were badly wounded in 2014-2015, with 35 fatalities (Health and Safety Executive (HSE), 2016). Accidents have a significant financial impact in the construction industry, which was estimated to be £0.9 billion in 2013-2014 (Health and Safety Executive (HSE), 2016). Automation, according to (Sharma 2011), improves equipment and employee safety, among other things. Computers are getting increasingly powerful, and they are learning to automate simple labor activities, reducing the need for employees with average talents and skills (Autor 2015). Automation is frequently used to replace labor, but it may also be used as a supplement to boost labor demand, therefore increasing profit and productivity (Autor 2015). Previously, motorized tools and earth-moving equipment had supplanted manual labor in the construction industry (Autor 2015).

The goal of this research is to look into existing and developing automation solutions that might be utilized to automate on-site construction activities using digital technology. Three research questions were developed to guide the research and concentrate the research objective: What can existing technology automate on the building site? What are the advantages of building site automation? What are the difficulties in adopting automation on the building site?

The objective is to identify appropriate and current technologies that may be utilized and integrated for on-site application in the construction industry.

Figure 1: Labor productivity in industry generally, and especially in the manufacturing industry is continuously rising; labor productivity in construction has been decreasing for decades. (According to Construction Industry Handbook 2012, Japan)

Construction Industry

The construction business is a massive industry that is extremely important to the global economy. The engineering and construction sector generates around \$10 trillion in revenue each year, accounting for roughly 6% of global GDP (Garca de Soto et al. 2018). For example, in 2004, the construction sector in the United Kingdom employed nearly two million people across 168,000 businesses and contributed £80 billion to GDP on an annual basis (Barker et al. 2004).

The construction industry is confronted with a number of pressing issues that have grown in importance as environmental concerns have grown, such as decreasing raw materials and energy consumption throughout a building's life cycle (Smith & Tardif, 2009). The construction sector is usually portrayed as one that is plagued by inefficiency, a lack of technical development (Lundeen et al. 2017), and an excessive use of raw materials and energy (Smith & Tardif, 2009; Bock, 2015). Buildings are unique goods that have gotten increasingly complicated (Oesterreich & Teuteberg, 2016; Eastman et al. 2008), necessitating multidisciplinary production and design expertise. Buildings must be built, designed, managed, used, operated, repaired, maintained, and demolished in more efficient, better, quicker, and less expensive ways (Smith & Tardif, 2009). Because of economies of scale and specialization in many areas of the building industry, prefabrication and pre-assembling are becoming more common (Eastman et al. 2008).

Construction plans, scale models, building permits, bills of materials, field reports, photos, warranties, as-built

drawings, material disposal certificates, punch lists, and a variety of other papers are all examples of information created by the construction business. These papers have not been consolidated onto a single platform, and there is a possibility that the same error will be made with digitization (Smith & Tardif, 2009). A building's paperwork used to consist of 30 to 40 pages, but now there are around four times as many (Krygiel & Nies, 2008). Using BIM, a complete building's design papers may be kept in a database (Krygiel & Nies, 2008). Instead of implementing contemporary technology, the construction industry's main issue is figuring out how to communicate and organize the information that is generated (Smith & Tardif, 2009).

Although the majority of building takes performed on-site, up to one-third of the work is done in factories (Smith & Tardif, 2009). Weather conditions, as well as the quality and availability of workers, are difficult to regulate (ibid.). The construction business is considered a craft (Smith & Tardif, 2009), which is one of the reasons why it has a low level of automation (Bolmsjö 2006). In the construction sector, there is a scarcity of statistical data, making it difficult to assess the impact of new technologies or improvements on productivity. Because the success or failure of new implementations is difficult to assess, the chance of innovation is low (Smith & Tardif, 2009). The lack of accurate business data might be to blame for the construction industry's sluggish rate of innovation. Furthermore, as compared to other industries, including farming, the construction industry suffers from a lack of technical progress and productivity improvements (ibid.).

The working conditions for an industrial robot in the construction sector include loose tolerances, inaccurate measurement, and significant workpiece uncertainties, whereas the requirements in the manufacturing business are tight tolerances, precise measurement, and stiff workpieces (Lundeen et al. 2017). Due to the wide range of activities performed and the presence of disordered materials, the construction sector is not in an ideal position to adopt industrial robots (Chu, et al. 2013).

On construction sites, tower cranes are widely utilized to move equipment, materials, and workers horizontally and vertically. Cranes are sensitive to environmental disturbances since they are used outside (Chen et al., 2017). Cranes need a vast workspace and have a significant influence on the overall construction project's efficiency and safety. Crane systems are inherently inaccurate, making control challenging (Chen et al., 2017). Crane operators bear a lot of responsibility since accidents have a huge impact on fatalities, injuries, costs, and timetable delays (Fang & Cho, 2017).

Automation in Construction

Although an industrial robot operating in the construction sector has access to a virtual model of the building, BIM, it is necessary for the robot to model and feel its physical surroundings as well (Lundeen et al. 2017). Among the goals of the study conducted by (Lundeen et al. 2017) was the development of mechanisms that would allow a construction robot to sense its surroundings and make adaptive decisions in order to execute labor tasks independently. A single camera and an algorithm were developed by (Feng et al. 2015) in order to enable a manipulator on a mobile robot to autonomously recognize and grab construction components and assemble the components into a modular structure that was previously planned. According to the research of (Chu et al. 2013), a robotic beam assembly system is provided in which a vision system tracks the locations of

the bolting of the steel beam to which the robot fastened the steel beams together is used to assemble the steel beams. The navigation of an Unmanned Ground Vehicle (UGV) in a dynamic and cluttered environment is accomplished by sending sensory information to a Fuzzy Inference System (FIS) for the purpose of resolving navigational difficulties (Almayyahi et al. 2017).

According to the findings of the (Labonnote et al. 2016) research, 3D printing technology may be effectively applied for large-scale buildings in the construction sector. This paper describes a novel routing technique for 3D printing ultra-high performance concrete that utilizes a 6-axis industrial extrusion printhead to extrude concrete layer by layer, layer by layer, via the printhead (Gosselin et al. 2016).

A complicated concrete wall was constructed in Switzerland's DFAB HOUSE, a modular research building where an industrial robot was used to complete the following process steps: erect formwork, install reinforcement, lay concrete, and strip formwork (Garca de Soto et al. 2018).

Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a term that refers to programs that are capable of making decisions in order to solve issues. Artificial intelligence may be utilized for a variety of tasks, including interpretation, perception, learning, reasoning, decision-making, and communication (Kumar 2017).

The key properties of AI are improved handling, adaptive control, and reusable knowledge.

For virtual reality, computer vision, robotics, image processing, automation, automated reasoning, pattern recognition, and process planning, among other applications, artificial intelligence systems have been created (ibid.). Machine learning (ML) is becoming more prevalent in industrial settings, and reduced barriers are enabling advances that are beginning to help the manufacturing industry (Sharp et al. 2018).

Additive Manufacturing

3D-printing have been attempted several times in construction for the purpose to reduce construction time, increase customization and improve affordability (Wu et al. 2016). Cementitious material that can be 3D printed is a promising and innovative construction method that have been growing in recent years (Ma et al. 2018; Wu et al. 2016). The 3D printing process works by adding material in layer by layer which builds a structure up via a computer designed file (Ma et al. 2018; Gosselin et al. 2016). Previously, additive manufacturing has only been used in biomedical and aeronautical industries due to high cost for materials (Gosselin et al. 2016). Additive manufacturing can reduce construction time, increase customization, reduce construction cost and manpower. Additive manufacturing is limited by the lack of development of BIM and large-scale implementation, life cycle cost and mass customization requirements (Wu, et al. 2016). Contour crafting is when the external and internal skins of the wall is 3D-printed and is later filled with a concrete substance (Wu, et al. 2016). Factors that must be considered are availability of printing materials, accuracy of the printing, printing time and the printing process cost (Wu et al. 2016).

Drones

Unmanned Ground Vehicles (UGV) are purpose-built transportation machines that are programmable and by using sensors information can be gathered and extracted from its surrounding without human intervention

(Almayyahi et al. 2017). According to (Tatum & Liu 2017), drones, or Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), are aircrafts which are unmanned and controlled by a pilot on the ground. Drones can also, more broadly, refer to equipment which is operated independent of human control. In recent years UAV have been easier to control, more reliable and less expensive due to technology advancements (Tatum & Liu, 2017). UAV can be used to inspect structures, quantifying material in landfills, construction monitoring and deterioration analysis (Freimuth et al. 2017). According to (Tatum & Liu 2017) 61 % of the construction industry in the U.S use UAVs in some way and mainly for video and photos. (Bouge 2018) said that in the UK the number is 12 %. Some risk can be avoided when using UAVs instead of for example inspections on scaffolds (Tatum & Liu, 2017). According to (Tomita et al. 2017), drones can be used for a task in building equipment works in which air volume is measured. This task is conventionally performed by workers where they have to manually approach the ceiling and take measurements of the air volume just under the air diffuser, using a handheld anemometer. This is a process which has low productivity and require extensive safety management. (Tomita et al. 2017) found that measurements, of satisfactory accuracy, can be made using a UAV in place of a worker, which is less time consuming and presents less risk of injury. For complex tasks that will be carried out by a machine, a vision system should be installed. Artificial vision systems can be used in automated inspection, vehicle guidance, surveillance, biometric measurement, traffic control and monitoring, robot assembly and analysis of remote images (Davies 2012).

Internet of Things (IoT)

As (Kochovski and Stankovski 2018) state, the Internet of Things' relevance when discussing digitalization and automation in construction is evident, as IoT elements such as electronic signalization, robotics, sensors, actuators, and other internet-connected devices may soon enable the development of innovative smart applications in the construction industry. According to (Bouge 2018), robots is projected to play a significant role in technical innovation aimed at overcoming the construction industry's present constraints, such as material waste and low productivity.

The Internet of Things is comprised of a variety of devices such as sensors, Radio-Frequency Identification (RFID) tags, mobile devices, embedded computers, actuators, and computers that are all connected via a global network. The Internet of Things may be used to create decentralized networks comprised of intelligent items capable of exchanging data and cooperating with other computer devices, people, and possessing some autonomy (Ochoa & Fortino, 2017; Zhang & Tao, 2017). The Internet of Things enables the collection and communication of real-time data within a system, making it more intelligent and increasing transparency and adaptability (Zhang & Tao, 2017). The Internet of Things (IoT) delivers solutions and standards that are Internet- and open-source-based and can collect data from any equipment or device (Georgakopoulos et al. 2016). Interoperability, connection, and integration are critical components of IoT communication systems (Buyya & Dastjerdi, 2016). It is critical to design a reliable computer system in order for the system to run without failure, which is a need for the scientific and corporate communities (Buyya & Dastjerdi, 2016). The IoT's primary difficulties include increasing the use of artificial intelligence, ensuring interoperability between

disparate platforms, developing easy user experiences, and data protection (Briodagh 2017). According to the existing circumstances, IoT devices must communicate with one another and with the internet (Buyya & Dastjerdi, 2016). IoT requires AI to analyze and understand data, as a significant volume of data will be created that cannot be managed manually due to the essential need of rapid decision making (Briodagh 2017).

Trillions of IoT devices might be connected in the future, which is far more than the current internet, which serves billions (Hofmann & Rusch, 2017). There are about 2 billion smartphones linked to the internet, and according to (Buyya & Dastjerdi 2016), IoT will reach 50 billion by 2020, and 20 billion by (Kochovski & Stankovski 2018). In the construction sector, the use of IoT can enable smart applications such as sensors, robotics, electronic signals, and actuators to be used in the near future to support monitoring, control, safety, cooperation, and supply management, among other functions (Kochovski & Stankovski, 2018).

A summary of the state-of-the-art implementation can be seen in Table 1.

Company	Key area of business	Possible to automate in construction	Automation benefits in construction
Fastbrick	Automatic bricklaying	Bricklaying on-site	safety, cost, accuracy, waste management, speed
nLink	Drilling holes on-site with coordinates from BIM	Drilling on-site	High accuracy, speed
Build-r	Automation in construction	Installation of drywalls, screwing	Increase productivity, reduce heavy and monotonous task
MX3D	Additive manufacturing	3D printing of steel bridges	Complex shapes
ETH Zürich	University: digitally fabricated house (DFAB)	3D printing for formworks for ceiling slabs, industrial robots that builds walls, Spatial Timber Assemblies,	Possible more efficient and sustainable
Komatsu	Construction equipment	Autonomous construction vehicles	Increase productivity and safety
Construction Robotics	Bricklaying	Semi-automatic bricklaying	increases productivity, safety, health and reduce labor
Odico	Produce complex architectural geometries	Cutting and milling complex shapes	Improve speed and efficiency

Figure 1: Build-r drywall installation robot

Figure 2: Example of an on-site robotic construction layout

Research in the Future

This article assesses the present state of digitization and automation in the construction sector, but it makes no recommendations for how to improve such elements. As a result, one of the most significant areas for future study might be how to effectively enhance the degree of digitization and automation in the building sector. More study might be done on how to standardize digital techniques to improve co-operability between construction businesses and the parties involved, as cooperation is frequently a good approach for quick development. Finally, research into the creation of automation equipment specifically designed for the construction sector would almost certainly be a huge help and facilitator in achieving higher degrees of automation. For the axis with the highest torque, research on integrating hydraulics on industrial robots in constructing a CR might be of interest, since the speed and precision could be balanced by the other axis.

Moving from the RP2 to RP3 will:

- Require huge amount of specific information related to the activity that need to be collected, organized, analyzed and updated continuously.
- Change in the construction processes.
- Impact the firm business model.
- Require innovative thinking beyond the robot, for example material
- Require different planning for site and logistics.
- Require safety practices that take the robots into consideration.

Figure 3: Robotisation Pyramid

Acknowledgments

The author would like to acknowledge and thank his supervisor Assoc. Prof Liu Yin from Mechanical Engineering Department of China University of Geosciences(CUG), Wuhan, China for rigorously overseeing the paper and special appreciation to China Scholarship Council(CSC) for granting scholarship to the first author at China University of Geosciences(CUG), Wuhan, China.

References

1. Albinsson, L., 2018. BIM Alliance 2018. Stockholm: Maestro Design & Management. Almayyahi, A., Wang, W., Hussein, A. & Birch, P., 2017. Motion control design for unmanned ground vehicle in dynamic environment using intelligent controller. *International Journal of Intelligent Computing and Cybernetics*, 10(4), pp. 530-548.
2. Autor, D. H., 2015. Why Are There Still So Many Jobs? The History and Future of Workplace Automation. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 29(3), pp. 3-30.
3. Barker, G. et al., 2004. *Improving health and safety in the construction industry*, London: National Audit Office.
4. Bellgran, M., Bruch, J. & Javadi, S., 2016. Characteristics of product introduction process in low-volume manufacturing industries: A case study. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 27(4), pp. 535-559.
5. Bock, T., 2015. The future of construction automation: Technological disruption and the upcoming ubiquity of robotics. *Automation in Construction*, Volume 59, pp. 13- 121.
6. Bolmsjö, G. S., 2006. *Industriell Robotteknik*. 3:4 ed. Lund: Studentlitteratur AB. Bonev, M., Wörösch, M. & Hvam, L., 2015. Utilizing platforms in industrialized construction: A case study of a precast manufacturer. *Construction Innovation*, 15(1), pp. 84-106.
7. Bouge, R., 2018. What are the prospects for robots in the construction industry. *Industrial Robot: An*

- International Journal, 45(1), pp. 1-6.
8. Buyya, R. & Dastjerdi, V., 2016. Internet of Things: Principles and Paradigms. Cambridge: Elsevier Inc.
 9. Carbone, G. & Gomez-Bravo, F., 2015. Motion and Operation Planning of Robotic Systems. New York: Springer Cham Heidelberg.
 10. Chen, H., Fang, Y. & Sun, N., 2017. A tower crane tracking control method with swing suppression. Chinese Automation Congress, pp. 3609-3614.
 11. Chu, B., Jung, K., Lim, M.-T. & Hong, D., 2013. Robot-based construction automation: An application to steel beam assembly (Part I). Automation in Construction, Volume 32, pp. 46-61.
 12. Dadhe, D., 2016. Research Methodology. 1st ed. s.l.:Archana Dadhe & Smashwords. Davies, E. R., 2012. Computer and Machine Vision. 4 ed. Waltham: Elsevier Science and Technology.
 13. Deng, Y., Hong, H., Deng, H. & Luo, H., 2017. BIM-based Indoor Positioning Technology Using a Monocular Camera. ISARC. Dupont, Q., Chua, D., Tashrif, A. & Abbott, E. L. S., 2017. Potential Applications of UAV along the Construction 's Value Chain. Procedia Engineering, 182(3), pp. 165-173.
 14. Freimuth, H., Müller, J. & König, M., 2017. Simulating and Executing UAV-Assisted Inspections on Construction Sites. The 34th International Symposium on Automation and Robotics in Construction (ISARC).
 15. Frohm, J., Lindström, V., Winroth, M. & Stahre, J., 2006. THE INDUSTRY'S VIEW ON AUTOMATION IN MANUFACTURING. s.l., IFAC Proceedings Volumes (IFAC- PapersOnline), pp. 453-458.
 16. Fulford, R. & Standing, C., 2014. Construction industry productivity and the potential for collaborative practice. International Journal of Project Management, Volume 32, pp. 315-326.
 17. Gagnon, Y.-C., 2010. Case Study as Research Method: A Practical Handbook. University of Quebec: Presses de l'Université du Québec, an imprint of Independent Publishers Group.
 18. García de Soto, B. et al., 2018. Productivity of digital fabrication in construction: Cost and time analysis of a robotically built wall. Automation in Construction, Volume 92, pp. 297-311.

© 2021 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

